

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

**MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND
NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT**

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**ASSESSING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NITROGEN OXIDES
AND GROUND-LEVEL OZONE IN LONDON**

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21 January 2024

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This Special Project titled: “**ASSESSING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN NITROGEN OXIDES AND GROUND-LEVEL OZONE IN LONDON**” is hereby accepted by the Faculty of Management and Development Studies, U.P. Open University, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree Master of Environment and Natural Resources Management.

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The special problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface.
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used.
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies and appendices.

Hilbert M. Libres

Acknowledgment

The completion of this special problem would not have been possible without the invaluable guidance and unwavering support of individuals. I would like to express my gratitude to Dr. Consuelo Habito, my SP adviser, for her guidance, insights, patience, and understanding. I also extend my thanks to the faculty members of FMDS who generously offered constructive insights, contributing to the improvement of this paper. Special acknowledgment is given to Dr. Manuel C. Manuel III for helpfully reviewing my draft, and to Michael Lagaya for the ceaseless support and motivation to finish my paper.

This special problem marks the culmination of my journey in the MENRM program, and I am indebted to the faculties-in-charge in my courses. Their commitment to sharing knowledge and providing resources has been instrumental in my learning. I extend my heartfelt appreciation to my brothers and sisters in ALNP, whose relentless prayers and encouragement have been a source of motivation during challenging moments. To my friends and above all, my family, I am truly grateful for their support throughout this journey.

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Abstract

This study analyzes the interrelations among ambient air pollutants – NO, NO₂, and O₃ – across London's four air quality monitoring stations representing urban background, suburban, roadside, and rural area areas. The dataset covering the study period from 2012 to 2022 was sourced from the London Air Quality Network (LAQN). Using the R programming language and the openair package, hourly concentrations were explored and examined, revealing daily, weekly, seasonal, and annual patterns.

Diurnal variations indicated that NO and NO₂ concentrations increased with increasing road traffic, while O₃ consistently peaked mid-day, highly influenced by solar radiation. The ozone weekend effect, where O₃ levels are significantly higher compared to weekdays, was notable in stations located in urban areas. Mean concentrations of O₃ were found to peak in late spring, possibly attributed to various factors such as heating emissions and stratospheric ozone intrusion.

Regression analysis showed significant decreasing trends in annual mean concentrations of NO and NO₂ across all four investigated stations over the study period. This reduction is associated with the active implementation of strategies and actions to curb emissions from the road transport sector across London. Due to declining NO_x levels, O₃ concentrations for the past decade have shown a significant increase.

The findings suggest a need for review and refinement of the emission control strategies in London, taking into account the complex relationship between NO_x and O₃. Further research into ozone weekend effect, seasonal influences, and the impacts of urban heat islands and climate change could inform targeted policies or regulations for air quality improvement.

Keywords: air quality, nitrogen oxide, nitrogen dioxide, ozone

I. INTRODUCTION

Nitrogen dioxide and ozone, alongside carbon monoxide, sulfur dioxide and particulate matter, comprise the primary air pollutants which pose adverse impacts to human health (World Health Organization, n.d.). The presence of these pollutants results from both anthropogenic activities and natural sources. Combustion or burning of fossil fuel remains to be the greatest contributor to air pollution (World Health Organization, 2021). The London Atmospheric Emissions Inventory (LAEI) 2019 data estimated that from 2013 to 2019 at least 90% of the NO_x emissions resulted from combustion (Greater London Authority, 2021). Road transport, on average, contributed to 50% of the annual nitrogen oxides (NO_x) emissions.

Nitrogen oxides are also emitted by non-traffic sources. The LAEI estimated that, on average, 18% of the NO_x comes from heat or power generation in the industrial and commercial sectors, while the aviation sector and industrial processes each emitted 9% of the total NO_x emissions (Greater London Authority, 2021). Previous research showed that NO_x flux was elevated in central London despite movement restrictions during the pandemic in 2020 (Cliff, et al., 2023). This observation is an indication that non-road NO_x sources, which are mainly from heat and power generation, influence exceedances of NO₂ concentrations to ambient air quality standards. London already has substantial policies for the reduction of traffic emissions, and focus should be shifted to abating non-road emissions.

Transboundary pollution can also affect air quality in London through long-range transport of emissions to the UK from other European countries. This has been explored in the study conducted by Stirling, Pope, Graham, Chipperfield, and Arnold (2020) using a model to quantify the transboundary contribution of NO_x to the UK air

quality. Apart from emissions coming from other regions in the UK, the study suggests that there is a significant contribution of transboundary pollution in London of about 25% of accumulated NO_x . This occurs during southeasterly flow with emissions coming from sources in the larger continental Europe and maritime emissions in the English Channel.

Ground-level ozone is a secondary pollutant formed in the atmosphere via complex photochemical reactions. NO_x and volatile organic compounds (VOCs) are the main precursors to ozone, which is formed under the presence of solar radiation. VOCs are released into the atmosphere from anthropogenic sources that include manufacturing and industrial processes, chemicals and vehicle exhausts. Natural sources such as plants and trees also emit biogenic VOCs. An investigation comparing VOC mixing ratios and VOC to carbon monoxide (CO) ratios in London found strong correlation between VOCs and CO (von Schneidemesser, Monks, & Plass-Duelmer, 2010). Findings indicated that majority of the VOC emissions come from traffic-related emission sources.

Owing to the presence of a wide range sources of these precursors and a hotter environment, urban areas experience higher levels of ozone especially during summer seasons (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2022). In the UK, elevated concentrations of ozone were found to usually occur in late spring and summer when solar radiation is high (Diaz, et al., 2020). A statistical analysis on ozone data spanning four decades conducted by Gouldsbrough, Hossaini, Eastoe, and Young (2022) revealed a drop in the number of extreme ozone episodes in the UK. The study found a strong positive relationship between temperature and extreme ozone events, and without reduction in emissions of ozone precursors, increasing temperatures may negate the lower number of ozone episodes over time.

Crutzen, Lawrence, and Pöschl (1999) presented an overview of the photochemical reactions occurring in the atmosphere which result to the formation of ozone. Ultraviolet radiation from the sun mainly drives the photochemistry of the troposphere which dissociates O₃ into O₂ and electronically excited O(¹D) atoms:

Ozone is formed again via the chemical reaction R2, and OH radicals are produced with the reaction between O(¹D) and moisture.

A series of reactions follows with the production or destruction of ozone and the reaction with nitrogen oxides. Most of the NO₂ in the atmosphere is formed via the chemical reaction R10.

In some regions, non-methane hydrocarbons (NMHCs) or VOCs may be the dominant source of OH radicals as simulated by Houweling, Dentener, and Lelieveld (1998). The study estimated that NMHCs contribute approximately 40% to net ozone generation. Reactions R11 to R14 are simplified photochemical reactions involving VOCs and NO_x (Beck, Krzyzanowski, & Koffi, 1998).

The rate of ozone production is limited by the VOC/NO_x ratio. At high VOC/NO_x ratios, or where OH generation rate is higher than NO_x production, ozone production is considered as NO_x-limited. In contrast, areas with NO_x generation rates higher than that of OH or having high VOC/NO_x ratios are in the VOC-limited regimes, as the case in urban areas (United States Environmental Protection Agency, 2008). The study conducted by Tudor (2022) concluded that ozone formation in London is in the VOC-limited regime, denoting that controlling VOC emissions can result to lower generation of ground-level ozone, and reducing NO_x at high NO_x concentrations may result to elevated ozone levels (Ren & Xie, 2022).

Due to the complex interaction between nitrogen dioxide and ozone in the atmosphere, a number of studies have investigated the correlation between these two pollutants as well as with other factors such as UV and meteorological parameters. A study conducted by Kovač-Andrić, Radanović, Topalović, Marković, and Sakač (2013) investigated the temporal variations in O₃ and NO₂ levels in Osijek, Croatia. The study showed insignificant correlation between O₃ and NO₂, but significant correlation between ozone and temperature and solar radiation. Another study using space observations was conducted to determine the correlations among NO₂ column, O₃ column and UV radiation (Dimitrievici, Constantin, & Moraru, 2017). A good correlation between ozone and UV index was calculated for China where NO₂ is substantially emitted from its huge industries.

Another study conducted by (Han, et al., 2011) analyzed the relationship between O₃ and NO₂ in Tianjin, China. The study found a polynomial relationship

between O_3 and NO_2 . The results of the study also indicated a diurnal cycle of ozone levels – increasing after sunrise with a mid-day peak and decreasing over nighttime. This cycle is a result of the photochemical nature of ozone formation. The same analysis using data from Campo Grande, Brazil (de Souza, et al., 2017) showed similar results. The study found that in this city, ozone level is influenced by both regional concentrations of ozone and by local primary sources of NO_2 pollution.

Li, Shi, and Chen (2021) investigated the spatial and temporal distribution of NO_2 and ozone in 348 cities in China and the relationships between NO_2 and O_3 . The study suggested an association between NO_2 and O_3 concentrations with both man-made and natural emissions. Analysis also showed NO_2 decreased while O_3 increased during the Covid-19 pandemic lockdown in 2020 when compared to 2019. This suggests that ozone formation in urban areas such as those in cities in China are mostly VOC-limited regimes where high concentrations of NO_2 are observed especially in highly developed and densely populated regions.

Due to their significant contribution to air pollution, reducing traffic movements and vehicular emissions play important roles in improving air quality. A study was conducted by Ding, Li, and Sze (2022) to investigate the impacts of implementing the London Western Charging Zone (WCZ) traffic congestion scheme. The study showed that WCZ scheme implementation resulted in a 31% decrease in overall traffic volume particularly in diesel-powered vehicles. Subsequently, road transport emissions are estimated to fall by 29%.

The report for the Central London Ultra Low Emission Zone (ULEZ) (Greater London Authority, April 2020) revealed that NO_2 concentrations at roadside locations decreased by 37% and NO_x emissions by 35%, which is equivalent to 230 tons, following ULEZ implementation which enforces strict vehicle emission standards.

Additionally, several studies were conducted to quantify reduction in NO₂ emissions in London or the UK because of the pandemic in 2020. Llaguno-Munitxa and Bou-Zeid (2023) found that NO₂ concentrations recorded at the stationary air quality stations across London following the Covid-19 lockdown decreased by approximately 30%. At urban traffic and urban background sites, NO₂ concentrations declined by 48% and 40%, respectively (Lee, Drysdale, Finch, Wilde, & Palmer, 2020). These reductions were attributed to a significant drop in the number of vehicles plying the roads of London after implementing Covid-19 movement restrictions.

A recent study by Tudor (2022) showed that ozone levels in London have continually increased significantly at an average of 19.33% annually over the years from 2016 to 2022. During the pandemic lockdown in 2020, ozone increased on average by 11% and 48% at urban background and urban traffic stations, respectively (Lee et al., 2020). The study found that although anthropogenic VOC emissions during the lockdown were significantly reduced, an increase in biogenic VOC emissions was inferred due to higher temperature and UV levels in the UK relative to pre-pandemic years.

Rationale of the Study

As mentioned earlier, several studies (Han et al., 2011; de Souza et al., 2017; Zoran, Savastru, Savastru, & Tautan, 2020; Kovač-Andrić et al., 2013; Jun, Yingjiao, Xingyao, & Weijun, 2019) have explored the correlation between nitrogen oxides and ozone levels in urban environments. However, it is important to note that these investigations assessed data over limited periods, ranging from 38 days to three years. This study undertakes an analysis of the correlation among NO, NO₂, and O₃

concentrations, specifically in London, over a ten-year period using continuous data and R programming language for analysis.

Objectives of the Study

This study is aimed at determining the complex relationship between nitrogen oxides and ozone based on observed data over a specific long-term period, which will help enhance understanding of the dynamic patterns and trends in NO_x and O₃ levels within London's atmosphere. The findings are intended to inform the development of strategies and actions aimed at mitigating NO_x emissions and regulating the formation of O₃ in the atmosphere.

II. METHODOLOGY

Data Source and Collection

Air quality monitoring data utilized in this study was obtained from the London Air Quality Network (LAQN). The LAQN's website serves as a comprehensive platform providing air quality information to the public. It includes detailed information regarding the monitored pollutants and monitoring stations which are strategically positioned across diverse locations in London. The LAQN specifically targets key air pollutants that are known to cause adverse effects on human health and for which ambient air limits or standards have been set. The measured pollutants include carbon monoxide (CO), nitrogen dioxide (NO₂), sulfur dioxide (SO₂), ozone (O₃), and particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}). Benzene and meteorological parameters such as temperature, solar radiation, wind speed, wind direction, relative humidity, barometric pressure, and rainfall are also measured in certain stations. LAQN boasts an extensive coverage comprising over 122 monitoring stations, with 112 stations dedicated to measuring NO₂, 109 stations monitoring NO_x, and 24 stations focused on monitoring O₃ (Mittal, 2021).

Data Collection and Selection

A representative monitoring period of ten years from 2012 to 2022 was selected to analyze data from the monitoring stations. Among the 122 stations identified, 22 are equipped with instruments that measure all three pollutants – NO₂, NO_x, and O₃ – relevant to this study. The specifics of these stations and their respective types are outlined in Table 1. Data from these 22 stations were retrieved directly from the LAQN database using the R programming language (R Core Team, 2022) through the

openair package, specifically designed for analyzing air quality data (Carslaw & Ropkins, 2012). For instance, the following R script exemplifies the process of importing data for all measured pollutants and meteorological parameters from the Kensington and Chelsea - North Ken Station (station code: kc1):

```
kc1 <- importKCL(site = "kc1",
  year = 2012:2022)
```

To provide a snapshot of the acquired data for each station, summary plots were generated, visually presenting periods of data availability and the associated percentage of data capture. The sample plot shown in Figure 1, representing station kc1, was generated using the following R script:

```
summaryPlot(subset(kc1,
  select = c(date, nox, no2, o3)))
```

Figure 1. Summary plot of NO_x, NO₂, and O₃ data from the Kensington and Chelsea - North Ken Station (kc1).

Four stations were carefully selected, each representing a distinct station type and exhibiting high data capture rates. The selected stations are as follows: Kensington and Chelsea - North Ken Station (kc1), Hillingdon - Keats Way (hi0), Greenwich - Plumstead High Street (gn3), and Reigate and Banstead - Poles Lane (rg3).

Table 1

LAQN Monitoring Stations measuring NO₂, NO_x and O₃ and their Data Capture

Station Name	Station Code	Type	Data Capture		
			NO ₂	NO _x	O ₃
Bexley - Belvedere West	bq7	Urban Background	86.7%	86.7%	87.0%
Camden - Bloomsbury	bl0	Urban Background	92.7%	92.7%	97.9%
Haringey - Priory Park South	hg4	Urban Background	86.3%	86.6%	86.1%
Kensington and Chelsea - North Ken	kc1	Urban Background	97.8%	97.5%	96.1%
Reading - New Town	rd0	Urban Background	91.5%	81.5%	92.4%
Redbridge - Ley Street	rb7	Urban Background	85.4%	85.4%	80.7%
Sevenoaks - Greatness Park	zv1	Urban Background	90.5%	90.6%	89.0%
Southwark - Elephant and Castle	sk6	Urban Background	91.2%	91.2%	91.2%
Thurrock - London Road (Grays)	tk1	Urban Background	97.9%	89.0%	93.7%
Greenwich - Eltham	gr4	Suburban	88.9%	88.7%	87.0%
Hillingdon - Keats Way	hi0	Suburban	97.3%	88.3%	96.0%
Richmond Upon Thames - Barnes Wetlands	ri2	Suburban	90.8%	90.8%	88.3%
Brent - Ikea	bt4	Roadside	71.2%	71.2%	80.0%
Greenwich - Falconwood	gb6	Roadside	97.5%	97.5%	96.8%
Greenwich - Plumstead High Street	gn3	Roadside	95.2%	95.2%	97.0%
Greenwich - Westhorne Avenue	gr9	Roadside	95.2%	95.2%	86.5%
Greenwich - Woolwich Flyover	gr8	Roadside	97.1%	97.3%	95.2%
Hackney - Old Street	hk6	Roadside	98.6%	98.8%	93.0%
Tower Hamlets - Blackwall	th4	Roadside	93.8%	93.8%	92.9%

Station Name	Station Code	Type	Data Capture		
			NO ₂	NO _x	O ₃
Waterloo Place (The Crown Estate)	ce2	Roadside	65.7%	65.7%	64.8%
Westminster - Marylebone Road	my1	Kerbside	97.2%	96.8%	96.3%
Reigate and Banstead - Poles Lane	rg3	Rural	98.2%	98.2%	97.7%

Data Preprocessing

Given the extremely large volume of data, exhaustive validation of individual points is not feasible. Therefore, the widely used Inter-Quartile Range (IQR) method, as employed by van Zoest, Stein, and Hoek (2018) for outlier elimination in urban air quality sensors, is utilized in this study. This method involves calculating the IQR as the range between the first quartile (Q1) and the third quartile (Q3). Outliers falling below $Q1 - 1.5 \cdot IQR$ or above $Q3 + 1.5 \cdot IQR$ were identified and removed from the dataset using the following sample script:

```
Q <- quantile(kc1$no2,
  Probs = c(.25, .75),
  na.rm = TRUE)
iqr <- IQR(kc1$no2,
  na.rm = TRUE)
up <- Q[2] + 1.5 * iqr
low <- Q[1] - 1.5 * iqr
kc1_outelim <- subset(kc1, kc1$no2 > (Q[1] - 1.5 * iqr
  & kc1$no2 < (Q[2] + 1.5 * iqr))
```

Concentrations of NO were calculated as the difference between NO_x and NO₂, and using the following script:

```
kc1$no <- kc1$nox - kc1$no2
```

To undertake an analysis of weekday-weekend and seasonal relationships between NO_x and O₃, data was aggregated using these sample scripts:

```

kc1_WE <- subset(kc1,
  format(date, "%A") %in%
  c("Saturday", "Sunday"))
kc1_wWD <- subset(kc1,
  format(date, "%A") %in%
  c("Monday", "Tuesday", "Wednesday", "Thursday", "Friday"))
kc1_season <- timeAverage(kc1, avg.time="season")
mean.kc1_season <- aggregate(o3 ~ kc1_season, season,
  mean)

```

Data Analysis

Temporal Variability

Determining the temporal variability of NO_x and O₃ is crucial due to the complexity of their reactions in the presence of sunlight. The variations of these pollutants across different times of the day and days of the week were plotted using this script:

```

kc1_timevariation <- timeVariation(kc1,
  pollutant = c("no", "no2", "o3"),
  normalize = FALSE, y.relation = "free",
  lwd = c(1,2), lty = c(1,1), ylim = c(0,80))

```

Welch t-Test

The Welch t-test was performed to determine significant differences between weekday and weekend concentrations of NO, NO₂ and O₃. This test, which is an adaptation of t-test for two samples having unequal variances, was conducted using the `t.test()` command in R. Prior to this, a variance test was undertaken to confirm inequality of variances between sample pairs. The variance test script is as follows:

```

var.test(kc1_WE$no2, kc1_WD$no2)

```

The Welch t-test was performed considering a 95% confidence interval having a null hypothesis that the true difference in means between weekday concentrations and weekend concentrations is equal to zero. The alternative hypothesis is that the

difference in means is not equal to zero. The t-test R script for ozone weekend and weekday mean concentrations, for example, is as follows:

```
t.test(o3~weekend, data=kc1_day, na.rm=TRUE)
```

If the variance was found to be equal, an option was added in the script to indicate such equality:

```
t.test(o3 ~ weekend,  
      data = kc1_day,  
      na.rm = TRUE,  
      var.equal = TRUE)
```

Scatter Plots

The relationship between pollutants was also analyzed using scatter plots. NO_x was plotted against O₃ using this script,

```
scatterPlot(kc1,  
           x = "nox",  
           y = "o3",  
           method = "hexbin",  
           cols = "heat", y.relation = "free",  
           lwd = c(1,2), lty = c(1,1),  
           ylim = c(0,120), xlim = c(0, 300))
```

while the following script plots NO_x against NO₂ with the third variable, O₃, differentiating weekend and weekday relationships:

```
scatterPlot(kc1,  
           x = "nox",  
           y = "no2",  
           z = "o3",  
           type = c("season", "weekend"), y.relation = "free",  
           lwd = c(1,2), lty = c(1,1),  
           ylim = c(0,130), xlim = c(0,300))
```

Trends

Trend for NO, NO₂ and O₃ were analyzed using the Theil-Sen method, a non-parametric approach based on Kendall's rank correlation (Nunifu & Fu, 2019). The

TheilSen function in R calculates regression parameters such as slope, uncertainty in the slope, and the p-values (Carslaw & Ropkins, 2012). Theil-Sen slope is estimated based on the assumption that the data points are independent and randomly ordered (Nunifu & Fu, 2019). Several studies analyzing the long-term changes in air quality concentrations have employed the Theil-Sen method (Li, et al., 2022; Chen, Rich, Masiol, & Hopke, 2023; Davtalab, Byčenkelené, & Bimbaité, 2023). The following is an example of the R script to perform Theil-Sen analysis:

```
TheilSen(kc1,  
  pollutant = "o3",  
  ylab = "Ozone (ug/m3)",  
  deseason = TRUE, ylim = c(0,80))
```

In this regression approach, data was deseasonalized using the Seasonal and Trend decomposition using Loess (STL) method. Loess is a regression technique used to fit points having nonlinear relationships (Hyndman & Athanasopoulos, 2018).

Annual means of each pollutant were also plotted using this sample script:

```
timePlot(kc1,  
  pollutant = "no",  
  avg.time = "year")
```

Exceedances

The aqStats function in R was used to derive data on exceedances of air quality objectives. The following sample script was used to calculate, among other statistics, the annual mean of NO₂, number of hours when NO₂ is more than the hourly mean limit of 200 µg/m³, and the number of days when the daily maximum rolling 8-hour mean O₃ concentration is more than the limit of 100 µg/m³ (Carslaw, Davison, & Ropkins, 2023):

```
aqStats(kc1,  
  pollutant = c("no2","o3"),  
  type = "year",
```

```
data.thresh = 0,  
percentile = c(95, 99),  
transpose = FALSE)
```

The Appendix presents images depicting the actual scripts entered into the R program, along with their corresponding sample outputs.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Temporal Variability of NO, NO₂ and O₃ Concentrations

The fluctuations in the mean concentrations of NO, NO₂ and O₃ over different time periods at 95% confidence interval are illustrated in Figure 2. These hourly patterns primarily result from the diurnal variations in the boundary layer and the pattern of anthropogenic emissions (Wang, et al., 2013). Notably, all stations consistently exhibited a diurnal variation of ozone, peaking from approximately 1 p.m. to 2 p.m. As sunlight intensifies in the morning, photochemical reactions increase the amount of ozone in ambient air, reaching their highest concentrations during mid-day to early afternoon when solar radiation is most intense. The rate of ozone formation declines as sunlight intensity decreases, continuing through the night. However, increase in ozone levels at midnight can be observed at KC1, HI0, and GN3 (Figure 3). This secondary increase can be attributed to localized emissions of ozone precursors like NO₂ and VOCs from road traffic and industrial activities. In contrast, this secondary increase is not observed at the rural station RG3 (Figure 2), where there are significantly fewer emission-generating activities. The scarcity of ozone precursors in this rural area leads to a continued decrease in ozone levels from early afternoon to early morning.

Figure 2. Diurnal variations of hourly NO, NO₂ and O₃ concentrations, µg/m³. Mean concentrations and 95% confidence interval in mean.

Figure 3. Day and hour variations of hourly mean NO₂, NO_x and O₃ concentrations, µg/m³. Mean concentrations and 95% confidence interval in mean.

Diurnal NO and NO₂ patterns showed an inverse correlation with O₃ concentrations. According to the complex reactions R1 to R14, in the presence of

ultraviolet radiation, NO_x levels in ambient air can invariably decrease as O_3 concentrations increase. Notably, NO and NO_2 concentrations exhibited the same hourly pattern with two pronounced peaks during the early morning and evening. The NO peaks correspond to the morning and afternoon rush hours when increased traffic volumes result to higher NO emissions. It should be noted that most of the NO_2 are secondary pollutants which are formed in the atmosphere via photochemical reactions. NO started to increase at approximately 3:00 in the morning and peaked at about 7:00 a.m. NO reacts with ozone (R10) and is converted to NO_2 , and with the presence of sunlight converted back to NO (R6) leading to the generation of O_3 (R7). After the morning peak, NO levels declined during midday at about 1 p.m. and reached its second peak after 6 p.m.

Figure 4 displays the weekly patterns of NO , NO_2 , and O_3 . Mean daily concentrations maintained a stable pattern on weekdays but distinctively changed on weekends. NO_x levels dropped during the weekends by up to 29% in KC1 compared to weekdays (Table 2). This NO_x reduction mainly results from reduced road vehicle movements on Saturdays and Sundays. Contrary to the expectation of a weakened ozone formation due to lower emissions of the precursor NO_x compounds, ozone concentrations rose during weekends as shown in Figure 4. Mean O_3 concentrations on weekends were higher by as much as 14% (HIO) relative to weekdays. This aligns with the findings by Sicard, et al. (2020), indicating a 12% higher average O_3 concentration during weekends in 808 urban stations. The phenomenon where mean O_3 concentrations are higher relative to the weekdays, even with decreased emissions of ozone precursors, is called the "ozone weekend effect".

Figure 4. Weekday and weekend variations of hourly NO, NO₂ and O₃ concentrations, µg/m³. Mean concentrations and 95% confidence interval in mean.

The difference in ozone mean concentrations between weekends and weekdays at urban areas (KC1, H10, GN3) were found to be statistically highly significant (p -value < 0.001), and statistically significant (p -value < 0.05) at the rural area (RG3) (Table 2). While the weekend effect is more evident in urban areas, it can also be observed in rural settings, albeit at smaller magnitudes (Schipa, Tanzarella, & Mangia, 2009; Huryn & Gough, 2014). Because ozone formation in London is VOC-limited (Tudor, 2022), the observed weekend effect in all four stations examined in this study may be due to high VOC/NO_x ratios resulting from lower NO_x emissions on weekends (Sadanaga, Shibata, Hamana, Takenaka, & Bandow, 2008). It should be noted that various factors like temperature, solar radiation, PM₁₀, and relative humidity (Atkinson-Palombo, Atkinson-Palombo, Miller, & Balling, 2006), and percent cover of developed lands (Zhao, Zhou, & Han, 2019) also influence this effect.

Table 2

Mean Concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$) during Weekends and Weekdays

Pollutants	Period	Monitoring Stations			
		kc1	hio	gn3	rg3
NO	Weekday	6.63	41.59	24.85	2.83
	Weekend	4.68	30.05	19.26	2.59
	% Change	-29%	-28%	-22%	-8%
	<i>t</i>	10.54	10.37	11.30	2.19
	<i>df</i>	2032	2123.9	2027.4	2116.7
	<i>p-value</i>	$<2.2E-16$	$<2.2E-16$	$<2.2E-16$	0.029
	NO ₂	Weekday	28.32	46.74	32.40
Weekend		23.58	40.22	27.42	12.02
% Change		-17%	-14%	-15%	-8%
<i>t</i>		11.06	8.52	11.04	4.49
<i>df</i>		1922.9	1782.1	1965.4	2132
<i>p-value</i>		$<2.2E-16$	$<2.2E-16$	$<2.2E-16$	7.57E-6
O ₃		Weekday	43.88	28.94	34.88
	Weekend	48.40	33.11	38.20	54.03
	% Change	+10%	+14%	+10%	+3%
	<i>t</i>	-7.02	-6.52	-6.28	-2.33
	<i>df</i>	1881	1787	1915.8	3939
	<i>p-value</i>	3.07E-12	9.37E-11	4.19E-10	0.02

Figure 5 illustrates the monthly and seasonal patterns of NO, NO_x and O₃ concentrations, and Table 3 provides the seasonal mean concentrations. Nitrogen oxide levels peaked during the winter (December – February) and declined during summer (June-August) at average concentrations of 19.2 µg/m³ and 13.6 µg/m³, respectively. The elevated levels of the primary pollutant NO during winter is attributed to increased emissions from heating of homes and buildings (Cichowicz, Wielgosinski, & Fetter, 2017). The same seasonal variation was observed for NO₂. Due to low levels of NO_x and sparse emission sources in rural areas, the seasonal variation of NO_x in RG3 was less pronounced. Similarly, the monthly variation graphs reveal an obvious seasonal cycle of ozone which is as distinct as its diurnal cycle. The average highest ozone concentration was 52.2 µg/m³, peaking in late spring (April or May) rather than in summer when solar radiation is more intense. Monks (2000) discovered that this spring maximum phenomena occurs across mid-latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere, with intrusion of stratospheric ozone and build-up of ozone precursors as one of the possible causes. It can be noted that ozone concentrations throughout the year were higher in RG3 than in any of the other stations. This is because in rural areas there is a deficiency in NO emissions which would scavenge ozone, as evident by the notably lower concentrations of NO in RG3. Nitrogen oxide concentrations in KC1 (urban background) were also lower when compared to HI0 (suburban) and GN3 (roadside) stations, primarily due to its location where there are no pollution sources nearby such as a busy highway. Munir, Chen, and Ropkins (2012) found that this variation of ozone concentrations between rural and urban areas can be related to traffic characteristics. The study revealed that buses have stronger positive effect on this variation than other vehicles because buses emit higher amounts of NO which scavenges O₃.

Figure 5. Monthly variations of hourly NO, NO₂ and O₃ concentrations, µg/m³. Mean concentrations and 95% confidence interval in mean.

Table 3*Seasonal Mean Concentrations ($\mu\text{g}/\text{m}^3$)*

Pollutant	Season	Monitoring Station				Average
		KC1	HIO	GN3	RG3	
NO	Winter	6.3	42.3	25.8	2.5	19.2
	Spring	4.7	28.3	20.4	2.4	14.0
	Summer	4.0	30.4	17.7	2.1	13.6
	Autumn	6.8	44.1	25.2	3.0	19.8
NO ₂	Winter	29.0	29.0	32.4	12.3	25.7
	Spring	26.4	26.4	31.3	13.2	24.3
	Summer	19.6	19.6	24.7	10.0	18.5
	Autumn	27.0	27.0	31.8	12.5	24.6
O ₃	Winter	39.2	25.8	34.3	53.6	38.2
	Spring	57.6	41.3	45.6	64.4	52.2
	Summer	50.6	33.3	37.7	53.8	43.9
	Autumn	37.4	21.9	29.4	44.4	33.3

Figure 6 and Figure 7 summarize the previously discussed relationships between NO_x and O₃. Figure 6 clearly indicates that higher ozone concentrations occurred at low NO_x concentrations denoted by the dark red section. Similarly, the yellow, orange, and red portions of the plots in Figure 7 highlight the same relationship that higher O₃ levels occurred at lower NO_x concentrations. The graphs also depict higher O₃ levels during spring and summer, as well as during the weekends.

Figure 6. Scatter plots of hourly NO_x vs. O_3 .

Figure 7. Scatter plots of hourly NO_x vs. NO_2 by different levels of O_3 split by season and weekday-weekend.

NO, NO₂ and O₃ Trends

Changes in NO and NO₂ monthly concentrations from 2012 to 2022 were investigated and are depicted in Figure 8 and Figure 9, respectively. Theil-Sen regression analysis showed a significant decreasing trend in NO ranging from 0.13 µg/m³ (RG3) to 3.36 µg/m³ (HI0) per year as an average, with p-values < 0.001. NO₂ exhibited the same trend with concentrations significantly decreasing across all four stations from 0.59 µg/m³ (RG3) up to 2.77 µg/m³ (HI0) per year. Over the years, London and the UK have enforced vehicle engine and fuel standards, hence the observed decline in NO_x levels. Euro standards aimed at reducing emissions of target pollutants such as NO_x, CO, and particulates from vehicles, have been in place since 1992 when Euro 1 standards were first introduced. Emission limits have become more stringent with the enforcement of updated standards. Specifically, the decrease in NO_x emissions observed for the dataset period was achieved through the Euro 6 standards which were implemented in stages from 2012 through 2019 (EU, 2012). London has also implemented traffic zoning schemes, namely the Congestion Charge (CC), Low Emission Zone (LEZ), and Ultra Low Emission Zone (ULEZ), which further contribute to the decline in NO_x emissions. All these schemes restrict the movement of polluting vehicles in most of the areas in Greater London. Moreover, coal consumption in the UK has been steadily declining since 2012 (Statista Research Department, 2023) and the total power capacity from renewable energy in England has increased from approximately 7.5 GW to 33 GW (Department for Energy Security and Net Zero, 2023).

In Figure 10, a decreasing trend is evident from the annual mean plots of NO. While fluctuations were observed in specific years and monitoring stations, an abrupt decline was observed across all four stations from 2019 to 2020. In London, there was

a year-on-year growth in vehicle miles travelled from 2011 to 2019, while plummeting sharply from 20.2 billion vehicle miles in 2019 to 16.5 billion vehicle miles in 2020 (Department for Transport, 2023). This drop in vehicle miles travelled, and consequently in NO emissions, is attributed to the movement restrictions during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Figure 8. Trends (Theil-Sen method) in deseasonalized monthly mean NO concentrations (2012-2022).

Figure 9. Trends (Theil-Sen method) in deseasonalized monthly mean NO₂ concentrations (2012-2022).

Figure 10. Trends in annual mean NO concentrations (2012-2022).

In contrast to the trends in NO_x concentrations, ozone exhibited an increasing trend from 2012-2022 as presented in Figure 11. It is evident from Figure 11 that ozone concentrations varied considerably between months and years, and this can be linked to the variability of meteorological conditions specifically solar radiation and temperature. Based on Theil-Sen estimate, ozone levels in KC1, HI0 and GN3 have increased significantly with regression p-values of less than 0.001. The average annual rise in ozone concentrations was 0.78, 1.11, and 0.32 µg/m³ in KC1, HI0, and GN3, respectively. This increase is consistent with the effect of decreasing NO_x emissions in all these stations over the years. As NO concentration diminishes, there will be fewer compounds to scavenge O₃ which leaves more O₃ in the atmosphere. In addition, London is experiencing the Urban Heat Island (UHI) effect where temperature in the urban areas can be several degrees warmer than the rural areas (Mayor of London, n.d.). With the climate change impact of rising temperature, the continued increase in urban surface temperature favors the formation of ozone. On the other hand, the decrease in ozone of 0.04 µg/m³ in RG3 showed a regression p-value of 0.78, meaning the change is not significant and hence ozone levels in RG3 can be inferred to be stable from 2012-2022. At lower levels, the reduction of NO_x will have insignificant impact on the already high concentrations of ozone in rural areas.

Figure 11. Trends (Theil-Sen method) in deseasonalized monthly mean O₃ concentrations (2012-2022).

Exceedances to Air Quality Strategy Objectives

Compliance with the UK National air quality objectives for NO₂ and O₃ was assessed by determining exceedances to established standards. In the UK, maximum allowable concentrations of air pollutants, averaged over different periods, were established for the protection of human health. At the same time, target values specifying the permissible number of exceedances were defined. The hourly mean limit for NO₂ is set at 200 $\mu\text{g/m}^3$ which is not to be exceeded more than 18 times a year. The annual mean concentration of NO₂ should not exceed 40 $\mu\text{g/m}^3$. For O₃, the allowable concentration is 100 $\mu\text{g/m}^3$ (8-hour rolling average) and not to be exceeded more than 10 times a year.

From 2012 to 2022, all four stations under evaluation exhibited no breaches of the hourly mean NO₂ limit. This finding is consistent with the LAQN reports (Mittal,

2021), which indicate almost no exceedances of hourly mean concentrations of NO₂. However, the annual mean concentrations of NO₂ exceeded the limit only in HIO from 2012 to 2019, as illustrated in Figure 12. The abrupt decline in 2020, falling below the limit, is attributed to the influence of Covid-19 restrictions and continuing emission reduction measures.

Figure 12. Annual mean concentrations of NO₂.

Figure 13 reveals a general upward trend of O₃ exceedances which aligns with the increasing trend of O₃ concentrations. The target value for 8-hour rolling average ozone exceedances was not achieved at RG3 throughout 2012-2022. In KC1, target was not met in 2012, 2018, 2020, and 2022. These non-compliances occurring at these stations are mainly linked to significantly lesser sources of NO emissions which scavenge O₃.

Figure 13. Number of exceedance days to O₃ UK/EU air quality objective.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

By analyzing the relationship among ambient air NO, NO₂, and O₃ in London over the period 2012 - 2022, this study demonstrated how the concentrations of these pollutants are interconnected, shaping air quality patterns in the city and its surroundings. Diurnal variations of NO and NO₂ were mainly influenced by anthropogenic activities, specifically vehicular road traffic movements. Similarly, photochemically produced O₃ followed a diurnal pattern, consistently peaking mid-day when solar radiation is most intense and increased at night due to localized emissions of precursor compounds such as NO₂ and VOCs.

Weekends exhibited reduced NO_x emissions attributed to decreased road traffic, leading to elevated O₃ levels during the study period. This ozone weekend effect is notably significant in urban areas where VOC/NO_x ratios may be higher. Winter recorded higher NO_x levels due to increased emissions from heating. Despite higher solar radiation in summer, O₃ peaked in late spring, influenced by other factors such as stratospheric ozone intrusion. Ozone concentrations in rural areas tend to be higher compared to urban areas due to lower ozone-scavenging NO emissions.

NO and NO₂ concentrations have shown a significant decreasing trend throughout the study period from 2012 to 2022 across all four investigated stations. Despite achieving substantial reductions through implementation of stringent emissions standards, traffic zoning schemes and increased renewable energy sources, O₃ levels have significantly increased. The study also revealed a general increasing trend of O₃ exceedances to the UK air quality objectives.

Based on these conclusions, emission control strategies in London could be refined taking into consideration the observed patterns and inverse correlation

between NO_x and O₃. Further research on source apportionment of ozone precursors, especially during weekends and late spring to summer, could inform targeted policies or regulations. Additionally, future studies on the influence of urban heat islands or climate change in London could deepen understanding of ozone formation, facilitating integrated actions for air quality improvement, urban planning, climate change mitigation and adaptation, and sustainable development.

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VI. APPENDIX

Figure A1. "Scripts to generate time variation graphs." R, 2024. Author's screenshot.

Figure A2. "Scripts to generate scatter plots of hourly NO_x vs. O₃." R, 2024. Author's screenshot.

Figure A3. “Scripts to generate scatter plots of hourly NO_x vs. NO_2 by different levels of O_3 split by season and weekday-weekend.”
R, 2024. Author’s screenshot.

Figure A4. “Scripts to generate trends (Theil-Sen method) in deseasonalized monthly mean NO concentrations.” R, 2024. Author’s screenshot.

Figure A5. “Scripts to generate trends (Theil-Sen method) in deseasonalized monthly mean NO₂ concentrations.” R, 2024. Author’s screenshot.

Figure A6. “Scripts to generate trends (Theil-Sen method) in deseasonalized monthly mean O₃ concentrations.” R, 2024. Author’s screenshot.

Figure A7. "Scripts to generate trends in annual mean NO concentrations." R, 2024. Author's screenshot.

Figure A8. "Scripts to calculate number of exceedance days to the UK/EU air quality objectives." R, 2024. Author's screenshot.

The screenshot displays the RStudio interface with three main panels:

- Environment Panel (Top Left):** Shows a data table with columns: pollutant, year, date, dat.cap, mean, min, max, median, max_daily, roll_8_max, roll_24_max, percentile.95, percentile.99, hours, roll.8.O3.gt.100, and roll.8.O3.gt.120. The table contains 18 rows of data for pollutants no2 and o3 from 2012 to 2020.
- Console Panel (Bottom Left):** Contains R code for creating and summarizing data objects:


```

      R 4.2.2 ~ /Library/CloudStorage/OneDrive-Personal/Documents/UPOU/ENRM_290_FS_2022-23/R/ENRM290_SP/ENRM290_SP2/
      > hi0_aqStats<-aqStats(
      +   hi0,
      +   pollutant = c("no2","o3"),
      +   type = "year",
      +   data.thresh = 0,
      +   percentile = c(95, 99),
      +   transpose = FALSE,
      + )
      |=====|100% -0 s remaining
      > View(hi0_aqStats)
      > gn3_aqStats<-aqStats(
      +   gn3,
      +   pollutant = c("no2","o3"),
      +   type = "year",
      +   data.thresh = 0,
      +   percentile = c(95, 99),
      +   transpose = FALSE,
      + )
      |=====|100% -0 s remaining
      > rg3_aqStats<-aqStats(
      +   rg3,
      +   pollutant = c("no2","o3"),
      +   type = "year",
      +   data.thresh = 0,
      +   percentile = c(95, 99),
      +   transpose = FALSE,
      + )
      |=====|100% -0 s remaining
      > View(rg3_aqStats)
      > View(rg3_aqStats)
      > |
      
```
- Environment Panel (Top Right):** Lists installed and available packages, including 'openair', 'nnet', 'parallel', 'pillar', 'pkgbuild', 'pkgconfig', 'pkgdown', 'pkgload', 'plyr', 'png', 'praise', 'prettyunits', 'processx', and 'profvis'.